

Class

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| ■ Actinobacteria | ■ Gammaaproteobacteria |
| ■ Alphaproteobacteria | ■ Gemmatimonadetes |
| ■ Anaerolineae | ■ Holophagae |
| ■ Armatimonadia | ■ Ktedonobacteria |
| ■ Bacilli | ■ Negativicutes |
| ■ Bacteroidia | ■ Nitrososphaerales |
| ■ Betaproteobacteria | ■ Nitrospira |
| ■ Chlamydiia | ■ Opitutae |
| ■ Chthonomonadetes | ■ Phycisphaerae |
| ■ Clostridia | ■ Planctomycetia |
| ■ Cyanobacteria | ■ Sphingobacteriia |
| ■ Cytophagia | ■ Thermoleophilia |
| ■ Deltaproteobacteria | ■ Thermomicrobia |
| ■ Fimbriimonadia | ■ Verrucomicrobiae |
| ■ Flavobacteriia | |